

EMERGE

Equipping Minoritized and
Emerging Research Institutions
to Grow Their Enterprises

NSF CAREER Award: Strategies for Success

A peer-reviewed EMERGE resource from the NORDP
Consultants Program

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About the NORDP Consultants Program

The NORDP Consultants Program is dedicated to increasing the diversity of the national research ecosystem by providing research development services to minority-serving institutions (MSIs) and emerging research institutions (ERIs) at no cost to the institution.

The program pairs research development professionals with investigators and research leadership to:

1. Strengthen researchers' capacity to compete for external funding,
2. Enhance research enterprise infrastructure and capacity,
3. Inspire institutional research cultures, and
4. Magnify the visibility and competitive reputation of MSIs and ERIs in the research enterprise.

Summary

The National Science Foundation's Faculty Early Career Development Program (CAREER) award is one of the agency's most prestigious grants and an investment in early-career faculty "who have the potential to serve as academic role models in research and education" (National Science Foundation, 2022).

Quick Facts

Title: Faculty Early Career Development Program (CAREER)

Opportunity Number: NSF 22-586

Funder: National Science Foundation

Budget: In FY19, 90% of CAREER Budgets were \$348k-\$800k

Project Period: Five years

Due dates for new submissions: Fourth Wednesday in July annually

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RD SAYS:

Look for these author notes throughout. They provide research development (RD) insights and best practices to help you submit a successful proposal/application.

PURPOSE

The Faculty Early Career Development Program (CAREER) is the **most prominent award** bestowed by the National Science Foundation (NSF) to junior faculty. Each award is meant to support a single principal investigator. The award's overarching purpose is:

1. To provide five years of extended financial support to individuals in tenure-track assistant professorships at the time of application;
2. As implied by the acronym "CAREER," to help an early career faculty launch a productive career as both a researcher and a teacher;
3. To incentivize colleges and universities to value the integration of research and education; and
4. To increase participation of those traditionally underrepresented in science, mathematics, engineering, and technology (STEM)

RD SAYS:

Don't let the prestige of the CAREER award discourage you. Consider the advantages you bring as an early career faculty at an Emerging Research Institution (ERI). The nature and strengths of ERIs go beyond supporting undergraduate research. Faculty at ERIs offer unique opportunities for direct engagement, mentoring, and fostering future scientists. Many ERI faculty have successfully highlighted these strengths to earn CAREER awards.

BACKGROUND

The first official NSF CAREER awards were presented in 1995 as a part of NSF's "intensified efforts to strengthen the Nation's science, mathematics, engineering, and technology (STEM) academic workforce by integrating research and education in academic environments" (Millsap et al., n.d.). To date, the NSF CAREER program remains the agency's "premier" funding program in support of the development of junior faculty into leaders in research and education.

Awardee Information/Success Rate

Reaching out to the program staff is a crucial early step toward an applicant's success. Program staff can help to identify the best program or funding mechanism for the applicant's proposed work. At the latest, the spring semester before you apply to CAREER, send a 1-3 page project summary that provides a basic overview of your project to the program contact indicated on the [NSF's CAREER contacts page](#) that corresponds with the program of interest.

The NSF CAREER is an agency-wide activity, meaning that programs across the NSF directorates participate. However, not all programs participate in the NSF CAREER, and **participation varies by program**. For

RD SAYS:

Be open to program staff's feedback, it may reveal other NSF programs or their directorate's standard grants that are better suited to your project. By being flexible and preparing early, you have time to make adjustments that will help toward your long-term success.

example, some directorates support one to two awards every couple of years, while others might support 10 awards every year. Additionally, funding rates for NSF CAREER vary by directorate and can range from 14-24%.

The data below for FY19 provides a snapshot of the number of CAREER awards made by NSF directorate and the average award amount.

Table 1. FY19 CAREER Awards by NSF Directorate*

NSF Directorate	Average of Award Amount	Number of Awards
Biological Sciences (BIO)	\$898,035	86
Computer and Information Science and Engineering (CISE)	\$459,536	174
STEM Education (EDU)	\$948,183	16
Engineering (ENG)	\$490,106	226
Geosciences (GEO)	\$584,385	62
Mathematical and Physical Sciences (MPS)	\$528,405	204
Social, Behavioral, and Economic Sciences (SBE)	\$549,511	38

* NSF typically provides and reports funding in annual installments. Above, FY2019 data are used because it allows us to approximate the total award size, which is not readily reportable from more recent years.

Also consider the data below on institutions that received more than one CAREER award in FY19.

ELIGIBILITY

Principal Investigator Eligibility

There are several eligibility requirements an early career faculty must meet to qualify for the NSF CAREER. These eligibility requirements are documented in the departmental chair letter (more details included below). To be eligible, a principal investigator (PI) must:

1. Hold a doctoral degree in a field supported by the NSF by the proposal deadline
2. Be employed in a tenure-track (or tenure-track equivalent) position at an eligible institution
3. Not be tenured (but in a tenure-track or tenure-track-equivalent position) as of the CAREER deadline
4. Have educational responsibilities at the eligible institution
5. Have not previously received a CAREER award
6. Have not had more than two CAREER proposals reviewed (i.e., an investigator may only apply for the CAREER award a maximum of three times)

RD SAYS:

Early-career faculty who have submitted an application for tenure are still eligible to apply for the NSF CAREER as long as 1) the promotion takes effect after the CAREER submission deadline and 2) they remain in the tenure-track position until October 1 following the deadline.

Institutional Eligibility

Institutions that are eligible to apply must be:

1. An academic institution in the U.S., its territories or possessions, and the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico that awards degrees in fields supported by NSF, or
2. A non-profit, non-degree-granting organization, such as museums, observatories, or research labs, if the eligibility requirements of the PI's position are satisfied.

Note that the NSF encourages proposals from different institutional types, including Minority Serving and Predominantly Undergraduate Institutions (MSIs/PUIs).

Additional Eligibility Considerations

An early career faculty may be eligible for the NSF CAREER, but it's important to consider whether the investigator's plans are aligned with this specific program or are better suited for a standard NSF submission.

CAREER plans are intended to be ambitious and an extended time commitment. Key questions to consider before applying:

1. Does the project have specific research and educational aims that are innovative and integrated?

RD SAYS:

Successful CAREER applicants have clear, complementary research and educational objectives that lay a foundation for their long-term goals. The proposal should integrate these goals seamlessly, positioning you in your field for the next 5-10 years. If integrating an education plan feels challenging, consider a different funding mechanism.

2. Do you have institutional commitment to support achieving these integrated research and educational activities?

The answers to these questions will help an early career faculty determine whether the CAREER is the most appropriate mechanism or if applying for a standard grant with a shorter time frame, that is more narrowly focused on research or education is the better option.

If deciding between applying for CAREER or a standard NSF solicitation, the PI should consider:

1. Can the research question or problem be solved within the five-year project period? Is the research question or problem, an important, logical next step for the field, that the PI is well-equipped and well-positioned to carry out? Is it supported by the literature?
2. How would the question or problem be approached over the first five years? What are the likely next steps after the end of the CAREER award? What would then be known that now isn't known?
3. What would be the well-constructed plan for integrating the proposed research funded by the CAREER proposal into the investigator's teaching?

For success with CAREER, all three of these elements must be present and well-defined.

ALLOWED ACTIVITIES

The aim of the CAREER program is to fund activities of early career faculty who have the potential to build a firm foundation for a lifetime of contributions to research and education in the context of the investigator's organization. Applicants must propose creative, effective research and education plans with activities that will help them develop in their careers as both outstanding researchers and educators. Research activities may be in **any areas** of science, mathematics, engineering and education normally supported by NSF. Activities will vary based on the proposer's research interests.

A wide range of research and education activities may be appropriate for the CAREER program. In addition to the activities described in the research and education plans, early career faculty may wish to include additional activities that address NSF's Broader Impacts requirement. Likely, the research and education plans will lead to outcomes that benefit society, however, there may be some activities that fall outside of the research and education plans. For example, these might include activities geared toward entrepreneurship and intellectual property, policy development, or other desired societal outcomes. To better understand NSF's vision for Broader Impacts and receive guidance on drafting a Broader Impacts plan, consider using an NSF-funded online toolkit developed by ARIS (Advancing Research Impact in Society).

RD SAYS:

There may be different expectations within different NSF directorates, which highlights the importance of speaking with your [NSF contact](#) to discuss your project. For instance, a proposed course-based undergraduate research experience (CURE) may be appropriate for one directorate but deemed not innovative enough for another.

BUDGET CONSIDERATIONS

There are a broad range of allowable costs that an applicant can include within a proposed CAREER budget. They include:

- Funds to hire a postdoctoral scientist, graduate students, and/or undergraduate researchers
- PI Salary

RD says: The PI should request a salary amount that is commensurate with the proposed scope of work, and justify why that level of effort is required to complete the scope.

RD SAYS:

Request a salary aligned with the scope of work and justify the effort needed to complete it.

- Evaluator costs

RD says: A plan for ongoing assessment of the proposed teaching-research program is important. It can be as elaborate as a randomized trial, or a before/after survey focused on certain attitudes or knowledge. Every application is expected to include some form of reflective ongoing assessment plan.

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- Domestic and international travel expenses
- Costs associated with hosting a workshop on campus, including covering participant travel, lodging, and meal costs.
- Consultant expenses

While there is no “one size fits all” when it comes to a CAREER budget, the key takeaway is that the funding request must be aligned with the scope of the project. It might be tempting to present a lean budget as a strategy for success, but in actuality a reviewer will be able to easily spot a budget that is misaligned with its objectives. A mismatched budget presents the applicant as rushed and may have the reviewer question the project’s feasibility. It’s also important to keep in mind budget minimums and maximums. All CAREER awards must be at least \$400,000 with the exception of those submitted to BIO, ENG, and OPP, which must be at least \$500,000. When there is no maximum amount indicated, talk with program staff to gauge directorate-specific budget expectations.

RD SAYS:

While the CAREER award primarily supports a single PI, you can allocate funds for interdisciplinary expertise. For example, a current awardee included modest stipends (<\$1K per person) for a small advisory committee to guide CAREER activities.

REVIEW CRITERIA

The NSF CAREER awards are reviewed using the two criteria used for all NSF proposals to evaluate the Intellectual Merit and the Broader Impacts of the proposed work. The NSF defines Intellectual Merit as “the potential for the proposed project to advance knowledge and

understanding within its own field or across different fields” and Broader Impacts as “the potential for the proposed project to benefit society and contribute to the achievement of specific, desired societal outcomes” (NSF, n.d.). Merit review criteria and elements are boiled down into a review form that all reviewers fill out. Both the Intellectual Merit and Broader Impacts are evaluated using the same five merit review elements:

1. What is the potential for the proposed activity to:
 - Advance knowledge and understanding within its own field or across different fields (intellectual merit); and
 - Benefit society or advance desired societal outcomes (broader impacts)?
2. To what extent do the proposed activities suggest and explore creative, original, or potentially transformative concepts?
3. Is the plan for carrying out the proposed activities well-reasoned, well-organized, and based on a sound rationale? Does the plan incorporate a mechanism to assess success?
4. How well qualified is the individual, team, or organization to conduct the proposed activities?
5. Are there adequate resources available to the PI (either at the home organization or through collaborations) to carry out the proposed activities?

The reviewers will assess the strengths and weaknesses of the proposal with respect to intellectual merit, broader impacts, and any additional solicitation-specific review criteria, if applicable. Additionally, for CAREER proposals, reviewers are asked to evaluate the integration of the education and research plans.

Reviewers will return written feedback on the strengths and weaknesses of the Intellectual Merit and Broader Impacts of the proposal as well as a subjective rating (Excellent, Very Good, Good, Fair, Poor). NSF does not provide numerical scores or have explicit “paylines.” Depending on the directorate/program, the proposal may be assigned a score for funding competitiveness – high, medium, or low competitive based on the reviewer feedback, alignment with program priorities, and fit with the existing funding portfolio (e.g., they are unlikely to fund two projects looking at the same thing). The review panel provides recommendations for funding to the program officers. Program officers then discuss the feedback and make their own recommendations, guided by the goals of the program and in balancing the portfolio (making sure a range of institution type, for instance) and other considerations like high risk and high reward. The Program officer decides either to recommend funding

RD SAYS:

Clearly address this in your CAREER application using a heading like ‘Integration of Education and Research Plans’ and a brief description. A graphic or chart can highlight the relationship between the education and research plans.

or decline. That **decision** is passed to the NSF division director, who either agrees or rejects it.

RD SAYS:

The review and funding decision process usually takes 6-9 months.

The NSF CAREER review panel may differ based on the NSF directorate or program, but it's typically comprised of experts across that particular field of study. Some programs will have ad hoc expert reviewers, while others will rely on a **review panel**.

RD SAYS:

Ask the Program Officer how CAREER awards are reviewed, but generally, write for an audience in your field, not just your specific subfield.

The NSF program staff have recommended that PI's reach out to the program director to discuss feedback after learning about the funding decision. The program director has access to the review summary and can provide helpful additional context to consider reviewer feedback and strategize for resubmission.

WRITING STRATEGIES

There are several unique proposal sections and distinct requirements that applicants should keep in mind when preparing a CAREER proposal.

Project Title

All CAREER applications must have a title that begins with "CAREER:..." followed by a brief description of the project that is limited to no more than 180 characters (including spaces).

Project Description

Because the primary purpose of a CAREER award is to advance a principal investigator's research and teaching goals, the project description—the 15-page narrative document through which the work plan for the applicant's CAREER project will be laid out in detail—has additional nuances and requirements that go beyond the standard guidelines indicated in the NSF's [Proposal & Award Policies & Procedures Guide \(PAPPG\)](#). The first **notable deviation** is that the principal investigator will be asked to provide distinct plans for both the project's 1) research aims and their significance and 2) educational aims and their intended impact. Both the research aims and the education are considered equally important.

RD SAYS:

A CAREER award focuses on career development, emphasizing the integration of education into your research. That's why both research and educational aims, along with their impact, are key.

Further, the principal investigator will be required to include a distinct section demonstrating **how the research and educational aims are complementary**, serving to collectively advance the principal investigator's career and departmental goal.

RD SAYS:

Education plans should align with your research, be achievable in 5 years, have measurable outcomes, and demonstrate clear impacts.

PECASE

Up to 26 NSF CAREER awardees will be chosen for an additional honor, the Presidential Early Career Awards for Scientists and Engineers (PECASE). To be eligible for this distinction, a researcher must: 1) Be

a U.S. citizen, U.S. national, or U.S. permanent resident at the time of nomination and 2) Not previously been awarded the PECASE. To confirm eligibility and be considered for this honor, the researcher must only upload a one-page "Additional Single Copy Document" that states, "I wish to be considered for the PECASE honorary award."

Reviewers will evaluate PECASE contenders based on three criteria: "1) performance of innovative research at the frontiers of science, engineering, and technology that is relevant to the mission of the sponsoring organization or agency, 2) community service demonstrated through scientific leadership, education or community outreach, and 3) commitment to STEM equity, diversity, accessibility, and/or inclusion."

Departmental letter

All CAREER applications must include a two-page letter signed by the head of the principal investigator's department or an equivalent organizational official. In addition to the signature, the letter must include the signatory's printed name and title. At some institutions, the signatory may be the Vice President of Academic Affairs or Dean of the Faculty.

RD says: The sponsored research officer will be able to provide additional guidance on who the best signatory is at the institution. Notably, each application must include only one letter. If a principal investigator has a joint appointment, the letter may be signed by both department heads.

The departmental letter is used to confirm eligibility and to give reviewers a sense for how the proposed CAREER plans impact and complement the department's goals. It also provides an opportunity for the institution to thoughtfully consider the ways in which it will offer ongoing mentorship and support for the researcher as their career advances.

The departmental letter **must include:**

1. A statement that confirms that the principal investigator is eligible for the CAREER status as of the application deadline by providing the applicant's current status as a tenure track, early-career faculty member. If the principal investigator is not in a tenure-track appointment, the letter must clearly indicate how the applicant meets the eligibility criteria for the CAREER award.
2. Confirmation that the principal investigator's research and education aims advance the goals of the department and that the organization is actively committed to supporting the researcher's goals and professional aspirations.
3. An explanation of the connection between the CAREER project, the principal investigator's professional goals and responsibilities, and the goals of the department and institution

RD SAYS:

Your sponsored research officer can guide you on the best signatory for your institution. Each application requires only one letter, but for joint appointments, it must be signed by both department heads.

RD SAYS:

This letter is not a standard support letter but a confirmation of eligibility and commitment of resources. Refrain from including more than the required details.

4. Details of how the signatory will ensure “appropriate mentoring of the PI, in the context of the PI’s career development and his/her efforts to integrate research and education throughout the period of the award and beyond.”

Given that the principal investigator is best positioned to emphasize the information that relates directly back to the proposed activities, it is typical that the principal investigator provides a first draft of this letter to the department head or organizational official.

RD SAYS:

Provide the Department Head with both your proposal draft and drafted letter to ensure strong alignment.

EDUCATION SECTION

This required information outlines activities relevant to the researcher’s discipline, interests, and departmental goals. An applicant has latitude in designing activities for any level of education. The NSF does not expect investigators to demonstrate an unreasonable workload in carrying out their project goals, as that would not foster sustainability. While educational aims are expected to be innovative and will entail some sort of a time commitment, be cautious of committing to overly ambitious aims. Educational aims and expectations vary by NSF directorate. A good way to determine if an educational aim is aligned with the directorate is to reach out to the program officer well ahead of the CAREER deadline. A well-argued and specific proposal for activities spanning the five-year grant term are expected. These should build a foundation for a *lifetime of integrated contributions to research and education*.

RD SAYS:

You can integrate the research and education sections in the Project Description, but if you don’t use a separate labeled section for the education plan, include a summary section. This helps reviewers evaluate the proposal and highlights key points of the education component.

It is important to keep in mind that reviewers will be experts in your field and mostly familiar with your research component. Some programs may also send your proposal out for review to education experts in your field and because of this, you should strive for a strong education plan grounded in the literature. You must cite relevant publications, state standards and local curricula if applicable, for example with a K-12 component.

RD SAYS:

If you are unsure about your education plan, consult a colleague in your institution’s education department, school or college. They are often good options to serve as external evaluators or help connect you with local schools for educational activities if your project includes working with students below the college level.

Examples of education activities include:

- Designing innovative courses or curricula;
- Supporting teacher preparation and enhancement;
- Contributing to museum exhibits or programs;
- Conducting outreach and mentoring activities to enhance scientific literacy or involve students from groups that have been traditionally underrepresented in science;
- Researching students’ learning and conceptual development in the discipline; incorporating research activities into undergraduate courses;
- Teaching a graduate seminar on the topic of the research;

- Engaging the broader public with your research;
- Creating cyberinfrastructure that facilitates involvement of the broad citizenry in the scientific enterprise;
- Providing mentored international research experiences for U.S. students;
- Linking education activities to industrial, international, or cross-disciplinary work; implementing innovative methods for evaluation and assessment;
- Designing new or adapting and implementing effective educational materials and practices, and plans for disseminating them;
- Build on, or otherwise meaningfully participate in, existing NSF-supported activities or other educational projects ongoing on campus; and
- Using new or existing tools to broadly disseminate your research and education activities.

A strong proposal will include plans for assessment and evaluation, and early career faculty are encouraged to collaborate with the appropriate experts. NSF recommends that applicants leverage existing [NSF-supported activities](#) or other educational projects on campus when possible.

SUBMISSION STRATEGY

Like with many other NSF funding opportunities, CAREER applicants should consider a long-term approach for success. As previously noted, the CAREER award is the NSF's most prestigious grant for early career researchers and consequently quite competitive.

While an initial application may be unsuccessful, applicants who are initially declined benefit from detailed reviewer feedback that can be helpful in revising and resubmitting the application. Further, NSF program staff are available and encourage applicants to reach out to them to discuss feedback in further detail to help with their next steps in addressing the reviewers' feedback and strategizing for subsequent submissions.

While considering a long-term strategy, it is important to keep in mind that applicants can only apply for a CAREER award three times. Additionally, researchers are no longer eligible to submit an application once they receive tenure. Therefore, each application should be carefully considered and prepared thoughtfully.

RD SAYS:

CAREER applications don't need existing NSF-supported activities to succeed. Instead, leverage institutional or community partnerships. For example, use an existing high school bridge program to create a STEM course for underrepresented students. Reviewers prefer early-career researchers to engage with established programs rather than starting from scratch. Show how your CAREER award adds value to these initiatives and consult with education experts to ensure your activities meet necessary standards.

Advice from Successful Applicants at Emerging Research Institutions:

- 1. Employ the NSF strategy to reach out to program staff “early and often” for feedback.** The NSF includes eight directorates, each with their own priorities and preferences when it comes to the CAREER award. What may be considered an innovative and acceptable educational aim for one directorate might not resonate with another. The typical budget range also varies widely by directorate. These are only a couple of the differences between the NSF directorates and their portfolio of CAREER award recipients. Reach out to program directors well in advance of the deadline (ideally at least by early May before the July deadline) with a 1-3 page synopsis of plans to invite a conversation about such talking points as appropriateness of scope and budget, the project’s fit with the directorate, etc.
- 2. Involve your institutional grants office early.** Most institutions have at least one institutional administrator dedicated to supporting the research endeavors of its faculty. In addition to helping alleviate the administrative burden of an application, this individual can offer crucial support with budget development, facilitating required institutional approval needed for federal grant submissions, offer feedback from both a layman’s perspective and from experience with the funder, and ensure that all application requirements have been completed to avoid the chance that an application has been denied due to noncompliance. Further, your institutional administrator may have access to previously successful applications that can be shared. If you are unsure of who this individual at your institution may be, a good starting point is either your grants office or the Dean of the Faculty’s Office.
- 3. Call on your colleagues.** A researcher’s network is crucial to success with the CAREER award among other funding opportunities. Consider those you may know who have had success with this funding opportunity or who may be able to connect you with others in your field that would be willing to share their tips and/or proposal samples. Further, reach out to colleagues early with draft sections of the proposal for feedback. A researcher may also want to consider soliciting feedback from colleagues that are outside their specialty because they can help to eliminate jargon and clarify points within the technical work that may not be readily understood from those in the scientific community that may be tasked by the NSF with reviewing the proposal but that are unfamiliar with some of the technical details of the researcher’s specialty.
- 4. Leverage other free resources.** There are a number of resources that are available to assist researchers in their pursuit of a CAREER award. OpenGrants is one such resource, an open-access database with a variety of sample successful proposals from a number of funding opportunities, including the NSF CAREER.

RD SAYS:

In addition to your grants office, check with your institution’s RD unit for support. They may offer resources like draft reviews, editing, peer reviews, graphics assistance, and competitive intelligence to boost your proposal.

5. A final, but crucial consideration for success with the NSF CAREER award is to **balance innovation with scope**. While research and educational aims must be innovative and transformative for the researcher and their institution, it must also be feasible. For new and innovative approaches and ideas, it's especially important to clearly provide support for why your plan is the best way to go and why it is likely to succeed. Be sure to describe the important milestones you anticipate on the path to success, include key supporting evidence that demonstrates the feasibility of your approach or idea, and demonstrate that you have a back-up plan if things don't go as expected. What is innovative and transformational varies by directorate, individual, and institution. Consider possible concerns a reviewer may have with the feasibility of the plan and gather feedback from both program staff and colleagues. Moreover, it is a common misconception that a reduced budget equates to greater likelihood of grant success. Conversely, it is also a common misconception that a researcher must ask for the maximum amount as to not "leave money on the table." Both are signs that the investigator doesn't know enough about research in their discipline to know what's needed to carry out a proposed scope of work, and are equally fatal to a successful proposal. A reviewer will easily spot if a budget is misaligned with the researcher's needs. The bottom line: ask for what you need to successfully carry out the plan of work.

TIMELINE

The CAREER proposal is a complex submission that requires dedicated time and effort for development. Begin early! It is unlike any other proposal and is very competitive. It is not unheard of to take 6 months or more to develop a strong proposal. At various stages of development you should be receiving feedback and incorporating that feedback into your proposal.

- **November before you plan to apply** (or about seven to eight months out from the July deadline) it's a good idea to assess yourself, your field, and the resources available while you brainstorm your idea. This gives you ample time to obtain necessary resources or expertise that you might need but don't already have.
- **By February before you plan to apply**, draft a short description (roughly one page) and reach out to a Program Officer at NSF to discuss where a good "home" for your project might be. It's essential to start this conversation early in case you need to adjust your plans for the project to better align with the program's funding priorities.
- **Between February and May**, block off a couple of hours each week to dedicate to drafting your proposal. Share your draft documents with colleagues for early feedback, even if they are outside of your subfield – their impression of your proposal might actually be more

similar to a reviewer's than someone working on a closely related project. If you know of others applying for a CAREER award, consider forming a writing group to provide support and accountability. It's ideal to have a full draft of your proposal ready for feedback two months before the CAREER deadline. Also, don't forget your budget! Work with your institutional sponsored research office to review budgetary needs and begin drafting a budget that reflects what you will need to carry out the proposed work. Your institution will likely require that your budget is approved before submission so initiating this conversation earlier ensures that a comprehensive budget with all the necessary institutional approval well ahead of the deadline.

- **In May, or around two months before the deadline**, you should also be drafting and requesting your Department Chair Letter. In your request, be sure to include your proposal draft so that your Chair can include important details about your project in their letter.
- **In June, the final month before the deadline**, you should focus on incorporating feedback, polishing the text and figures, and preparing the supplemental application documents.

Application Components and Timing Considerations

There are many important components of the proposal including:

- Cover Sheet,
- Project Summary,
- Project Description,
- Budget and Budget Justification,
- References,
- Departmental letter,
- Biosketches,
- Current and Pending Support, Facilities,
- Equipment and Other Resources,
- Data Management Plan,
- Mentoring plan for postdoctoral researchers and/or graduate students (if applicable),
- Letters of collaboration (if collaborative arrangements are significant), and a
- Proposal Classification form (only for the BIO directorate).

These all take considerable time to develop and investigators should be aware of these needs as early as possible. Some of the key time-consuming areas for planning and development are:

1. Having a conversation with the appropriate Program Officer and incorporating feedback.
2. Understanding the mission of the NSF and what has been funded by the CAREER program in the past.
3. Developing and articulating your research and education vision for the next ten to twenty years, and an initial five-year plan for achieving that research vision.
4. Having peers and others read and comment on your drafts and allowing time to incorporate that feedback.
5. Establishing industry collaborations when these may be helpful.
6. Working with institutional staff on timeline with deliverables, being clear on roles and responsibilities.
7. Developing the narrative sections of the proposal.
8. Developing a budget and budget justification that is reasonable and clearly related to each of your program milestones.
9. Developing high quality graphics to illustrate your ideas.
10. Developing a timeline for your research and education activities to build into your proposal.

RESOURCES TO SUPPORT THE DEVELOPMENT OF A COMPETITIVE APPLICATION:

- **Read previously successful proposals.** Use the [NSF awards database](#), to look for familiar names, and ask for a copy of their proposal. Many recipients are happy to share, and it can be very helpful to see the scope of work proposed across five years and the corresponding budget. Alternatively, the [Open Access repository](#) is a valuable and unique resource containing proposals submitted and funded by NSF and others.
- **Join a writing support group or program.** [The Colleges of Liberal Arts Sponsored Programs \(CLASP\)](#) is a free community of practice for grants administrators at Emerging Research Institutions. There are over 300 institutions and more than 700 individual members currently subscribed to the list, many of whom are actively involved in offering support for those supporting faculty research applications like the NSF CAREER. CLASP hosts a variety of in-person and virtual programs annually and has saved several recorded versions of past events for subscribers and their researchers to benefit from. This includes a recording of a panel discussion that featured successful CAREER awardees from Emerging Research Institutions. Applicants can gain access to this resource and more by subscribing to CLASP.

TIMELINE: DESK GUIDE

	November	December	January	February	March	April	May	June	July
NSF Career Award Deadline Fourth Wednesday in July									
Assess yourself, your field, and available resources; brainstorm ideas.									
Draft a one-page description; contact an NSF Program Officer to discuss program alignment.									
Dedicate time weekly to drafting your proposal; seek feedback from colleagues and form a writing group if possible.									
Have a full draft ready for feedback; finalize your budget with your sponsored research office.									
Request your Department Chair Letter and provide your proposal draft for reference.									
Incorporate feedback, polish text and figures, and prepare supplemental documents.									
Submit your final proposal before the NSF CAREER deadline.									

AUTHORS

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The background is a solid blue color with a complex, abstract pattern of thin, white, curved lines that flow and swirl across the page, creating a sense of movement and depth. The lines are most concentrated in the lower half of the image, where they form a dense, grid-like structure that tapers and curves upwards.

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